

AI4

Final Communication, training, outreach, dissemination and collaboration/liaison and exploitation plans and results

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1 HIGHLIGHTS OF THE ACHIEVED RESULTS

The highlights below focus only on the most important achievements in terms of communication, dissemination, exploitation and collaboration perspectives, since the beginning of the project

- We have established **collaborations with 15 projects**, both in the **INFRAEOSC ecosystem** (RAISE, FAIR-EASE, FAIR-IMPACT, BlueCloud 2026, EOSC Cancer, EOSC Future, EOSC DIH, Skills4EOSC), in a more **wider Horizon Europe context** (iImagine, AI4Life, AI4EU and AI-on-demand, European AI Security Network - EASiNet) and with **relevant industrial partners** (NVIDIA, Flower.ai).
 - Projects already exploiting AI4EOSC results include AI-on-demand, iImagine and AI4Life.
 - Projects that are under further agreement on exploiting AI4EOSC include RAISE, BlueCloud 2026, iImagine and AI4Life.
- AI4EOSC has actively participated in the EOSC Ecosystem horizontal collaboration activities, including the participation in the EOSC Focus HE Technology, HE Impact, HE Communication and Engagement Working Groups, and the organized events of the EC and EOSC Association. We have actively engaged with all the open consultations and calls for participation from the EOSC Association.
- Up to date, and in the context of the AI4EOSC actions, consortium partners have **published 16 scientific articles** (exceeding the established KPI) in **high quality journals** (like Neurocomputing, Journal of Grid Computing, Water Research, Future Generation Computer Systems, Nature Scientific Data or Automation in Construction) and conference proceedings.
- AI4EOSC has **organized and delivered 5 workshops** with special focus on end users and user communities (2 in person, 3 available online)
- AI4EOSC has been **represented in more than 20 relevant events** (including more than **41 presentations, posters and demonstrations**), also being **invited to 2 specialized workshops on research infrastructures** (RICH Symposium, ESFRI-EOSC Policy Workshop on "FAIR Data Productivity and Advanced Digitalization")

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 PURPOSE

The purpose of this document is to update the “communication, training, outreach, dissemination and collaboration/liaison and exploitation plans” that have been presented in D2.2, and present the results of the activities so far.

An exploitation and dissemination plan is an important part of any research project, and it is particularly important for a project like AI4EOSC that aims to promote the use of AI tools and services within the EOSC. A well-designed communication and dissemination plan can help to ensure that the project's goals and achievements are widely known and understood by key audiences, and that the project's results are used and applied in ways that maximize their potential impact and benefits to society.

The purpose of such a plan is to promote the project's goals and achievements, to create synergies and coordinate activities with other initiatives and projects, and to ensure the impact of the project through industrial and scientific collaboration and outreach and training.

The plan proposed in the D2.2 has been updated, and in addition we have described the achieved results. This deliverable presents the strategy in this respect till the end of the project.

2.2 DOCUMENT ORGANIZATION

This document outlines how the project's results will be used and shared with key audiences, in order to maximize their potential impact and benefits.

The [Exploitation Plan](#) section outlines the objectives and methodology for exploiting the project's results, including the exploitable results that will be generated by the project and the roles and responsibilities of project partners in managing and exploiting these outputs. The section also includes information about the activities carried out to support the exploitation of the project's results, such as training and capability building, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management, and managing exploitation results. The section also describes the methods used to monitor the progress and success of the exploitation plan. The exploitation plan compared to the deliverable D2.2 includes updated Key Exploitable Results (KERs).

The [Dissemination Plan](#) section outlines the objectives and methodology for disseminating information about the project and its results to key audiences. It includes information about the target audience for the project's results, as well

as the roles and responsibilities of project partners in disseminating information about the project. The section also describes the instruments and channels used to share information about the project, such as the project's website, social media channels, and events. The section also includes information about how the effectiveness of the dissemination plan is monitored, with the monitoring results. It also describes collaboration with other projects and initiatives as well as the events that have been organized by AI4EOSC.

Finally, the document includes [annexes](#) with additional information, such as definitions of key terms and the branding kit for the project, a list of scientific publications , a list of the events attended or planned and a list of other dissemination activities.

3 EXPLOITATION PLAN

3.1 OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

The exploitation goal is to support the promotion of AI4EOSC results and their use to maximize the expected impacts of the project. This section will therefore outline the actions that are taken to make use of the project results for scientific and commercial purposes in further research activities beyond those covered in AI4EOSC project use cases.

The exploitation plan for the AI4EOSC project will be implemented with the following principles:

1. **Publishing project results under open licenses** aiming at open-source software developments and the delivery of operational services that can be exploited following the cloud computing service model.
2. **Engaging stakeholders** by the customisation of proposed solutions in the selected use cases and reaching external ones (e.g. exploitation activities in R&D projects like iMagine).
3. **Delivering services with easy adaptation/integration** achieved by the provisioning of new high-level services and functionalities.
4. **Targeting long-term exploitation** by integrating project outputs:
 - a. into upstream software products (e.g. contributions to major open source solutions, like Flower.ai).

- b. into use case related products (e.g. integration with institutional or national initiatives, like the existing Polish national agriculture platform for the integrated plant protection use case).
 - c. into the more global architecture of the EOSC and the evolving EOSC Nodes federation, or the AlonDemand (AloD) ecosystem.
5. **Using the project results also for academic purposes** (Master, PhD, post-PhD) supported by several academic partners that have already developed key components used in the production of EU e-Infrastructures.

3.2 EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

We have identified five Key Exploitable Results (KER), which are described below, that are monitored and updated during the project’s lifetime. Exploitable results, as well as the relevant stakeholders and the possible exploitation plans are listed below, and are being tracked on the project confluence under the link². It is worth noticing that the KER2 has been renamed already in the previous reporting area, to “AI4OS software stack”, as it better reflects the KER and its purpose. The description has also been updated accordingly.

During the course of the project we will also, as part of the exploitation and innovation management, analyze and try to identify any other exploitable results and will describe them in a similar way.

Table 1. KER1: AI4EOSC Platform

Result type	Software and services.
URL	https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/services/eosc.ifca-csic.ai4eosc_platform
Key innovation	Next generation AI platform implementing advanced features such as federated or split learning.
Target audiences	Researchers, AI service providers.
Key benefit (for the audiences)	Generic-value service, allowing scientists to develop and service applications easily

² <https://confluence.ifca.es/display/AI4/Key+Exploitable+Results>

Key exploitation paths	Direct exploitation (for researchers) through the EOSC EU Node Registry and portal (free basis during project lifetime). Subscription-based, pay-per-use and pay-per-data volume or individual contract to adapt the service.
IPR approach	Project software based on open source licenses. Service offer does not require Intellectual Property (IP) transfer.
Result description	Modular, reusable, integrable, composable set of components integrated into a pilot platform. The EOSC-based cloud platform will allow developing machine learning and deep learning applications that require distributed and federated learning as well as composite scenarios in order to build more complex applications and models.
Result Maturity	TRL 8
Do you already have customers for this result?	This platform supersedes the DEEP-Hybrid-DataCloud EOSC compute platform and services ³ . Customers are the current EOSC users that discover services from a variety of different providers. We are also offering the services and platform for other user communities and projects (iImagine, INFRAEOSC projects).
What type of customers/ users do you have?	Researchers and service providers from different areas.

³ https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/services/eosc.ifca-csic.deepaas_training_facility

Which Business Sectors do your customers mainly come from?	Engineering & Technology, Natural Sciences, Generic Humanities, Agricultural Sciences, Humanities, Social Sciences, ...
Unique value proposition	The project facilitates the development of new techniques and methodologies to effectively exploit large, distributed and heterogeneous datasets by researchers in the upcoming years, anticipating the needs of complex AI applications.

Table 2. KER2: AI4OS Software Stack

Result type	Software and services, Business Models.
URL	https://ai4os.eu https://github.com/ai4os
Key innovation	Reduced time-to-market for SME and industry developing AI/ML/DL applications, private platform or platforms to build a service.
Target audiences	Service providers, SMEs, innovators, start-ups.
Key benefit (for the audiences)	More and better services for faster and higher quality on-premises deployments, automated and customized platforms tailored to specific stakeholder needs.
Key exploitation paths	Depending on the specific case, it could be subscription-based, pay per data volume or pay for deployment of the service.
IPR approach	Project software based on open source licenses. Service offer does not require IP transfer.

Result description	<p>Generic software stack (named AI4OS) with easy customization paths to create a customized AI4EOSC compatible platform across multiple Cloud back-ends (through manual deployment or by using the INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator together with the Infrastructure Manager).</p> <p>Extension to the existing DEEP platform in order to ease the customization path both for researchers and for the exploitation of the deployed services.</p>
Result Maturity	TRL 8
Do you already have customers for this result?	AI4EOSC communities
What type of customers/ users do you have?	Researchers, service providers from different areas.
Unique value proposition	Allow organizations to create custom platforms by using the AI4OS software stack, with the possibility of consuming services from the AI4EOSC platform, remaining compatible with it.

Table 3. KER3: AI4EOSC Catalogue

Result type	AI models, Software and services.
URL	https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/marketplace https://github.com/ai4os-hub
Key innovation	Increased service offer and capabilities beyond the present landscape in addressing the current and anticipated needs of the research community at large.
Target audiences	Researchers, SMEs, innovators, start-ups.

Key benefit (for the audiences)	Services addressing the current and anticipated needs of the research community at large.
Key exploitation paths	Individual contracts for using or adapting the application.
IPR approach	Project software based on open source licenses, and other assets with CC-BY.
Result description	<p>Delivery of a public catalogue of services following the layered cloud service model (IaaS, PaaS, FaaS, SaaS) exploiting in a structural way resources coming from these different layers in the cloud-based EOSC resources.</p> <p>Providing rich services to build and deploy customizable machine learning, deep learning and artificial intelligence applications following a platform and serverless approach with horizontal scalability over the EOSC continuum.</p>
Result Maturity	TRL 8
Do you already have customers for this result?	Services can be customized and integrated with the existing workflows of researchers across different disciplines.
What type of customers/ users do you have?	Researchers, service providers from different areas.
Unique value proposition	Immediate adoption of an application that has provided a usable solution in a similar case.

Table 4. KER4: AI4EOSC Exchange

Result type	Policies and best practices
Key innovation	Transforming the way the audience creates, shares and exploits research outputs (data, publications, protocols, methodologies, software, code, etc.) within and across research disciplines, leading to better quality, validation, more innovation and higher productivity of research.
Target audiences	Researchers, educators, EOSC and AI4EU communities, Digital innovation Hubs (DIHs), Policy Makers and Private companies.
Key benefit (for the audiences)	Improvement in AI/ML/DL development for research, innovation providing readiness to exploit EOSC assets.
Key exploitation paths	Expertise and consultancy services, individual contracts.
IPR approach	Offered with an open license. Consultancy as a service, no IP transfer.
Result description	An EOSC AI exchange and community of practice around AI/ML/DL application development and deployment at scale, including but not limited to a noticeable knowledge body in the form of best practices, documentation and publications.
What type of customers/ users do you have?	Researchers, service providers from different areas.
Which Business Sectors do your customers mainly come from?	Engineering & Technology, Natural Sciences, Generic Humanities, Agricultural Sciences, Humanities, Social Sciences

Unique value proposition	Co-design activities from the early beginning of the project development phases. The consortium has proven experience on fostering DevOps practices in order to better cooperate with user communities thus providing an easy path towards the effective deployment of the developed tools.
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Table 5. KER5: AI4EOSC Models and technological solutions

Result type	Software and services.
Key innovation	Integrating use cases results with commercial products or well-established public platforms.
Target audiences	SMEs, innovators, startups, research communities and AI/ML/DL practitioners and application developers. Public domain, initiatives in agriculture and environmental protection.
Key benefit (for the audiences)	Wider adoption of AI/ML/DL techniques for non-practitioners to provide insights on scientific data.
Key exploitation paths	Depending on the specific case, it could be subscription-based, pay per data volume or pay for deployment of the service.
IPR approach	Software tools that will be delivered in the portal are based on open-source licenses.
Result description	Domain-specific AI models and technological solutions for the leading use cases (e.g. in agriculture, thermography) targeted for direct exploitation by scientists and scientific teams.

Result Maturity	TRL 7
Do you already have customers for this result?	Yes, we have (e.g. integrating UC2 from WODR in eDWIN).
Unique value proposition	Application of ML/DL technologies use case results to provide solutions for economic and societal sectors.

3.3 ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

In relation to specific consortium members assignment, the results exploitation will be particularly covered by WP2. As this Work Package leader, PSNC supports the innovation and exploitation activities of the project.

The key roles in the results management and exploitation of AI4EOSC project and their responsibilities are as follows:

Work Package (WP) leaders

- To register and update project results on AI4EOSC related software repositories: <https://github.com/AI4EOSC>.
- To ensure that dissemination and exploitation plans are defined by the main responsible of the result.

Main Responsible of PR

- In collaboration with the WP leader, registration of information on the project results in the exploitation Confluence webspace, including exploitation and dissemination plans⁴.
- To provide input on the work performed, achievements, problems encountered, unexpected risks and corrective actions taken, and deviations from the original Description of the Action.
- To Advise on the best approach to protect Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) for the results produced during the project.

Project Management Board (PMB)

- To review periodically the list of aggregated results.
- Validation of the key exploitable results, and review the dissemination and exploitation plan execution.

⁴ <https://confluence.ifca.es/display/AI4/Key+Exploitable+Results>

Project coordinator

- Approve the exploitation plan

3.4 ACTIVITIES

This section presents exploitation activities that aim at further maximizing the impact of the project results. It covers the description of tutorials and training, management of IPR and exploitation outputs that adhere to the FAIR data and research principle.

3.4.1 Training, documentation and capability building

One of the important activities that will facilitate the dissemination and exploitation of the project results is knowledge transfer in the form of training.

Prepared training courses and materials will cover different results of the projects including the Key Exploitable Results.

AI4EOSC for the purpose of training follows the EOSC-Synergy project⁵ approach and reuses tools developed and deployed in this project for the EOSC ecosystem and maintained by PSNC. We expect to provide the MOOC Courses that will focus on usage of the results of the project, as well as in-person tutorials provided in conjunction with organized events. AI4EOSC will use the [Learn@Synergy](https://learn.eosc-synergy.eu/)⁶ platform that consist of Modular set of tools for preparing and conducting tutorials ^[1]_[SEP]:

- MOOC: customised Moodle
- Video Conference facility for trainings
- [Training material catalogue](https://learn.eosc-synergy.eu/catalogue/)⁷

In addition the platform already includes several courses related to EOSC, but also it contains the Guidance and best practice for creating good quality tutorials.

⁵ <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/technical-areas/e-learning/>

⁶ <https://learn.eosc-synergy.eu/>

⁷ <https://learn.eosc-synergy.eu/catalogue/>

Figure 1. Learn@Synergy platform - handbook page

In the first year we were focusing on preparation of the materials, building blocks for courses to be developed in the 2nd year of the project.

On the [User HowTo⁸](#) documentation, there are training materials for users (linked in the training material catalogue). They are covering the following subjects:

- Try a model (from the Dashboard, locally)
- Develop a model (develop, use MLflow, use advanced training techniques, ...)
- Train a model (train a model, using the federated server, using rclone, ...)
- Deploy a model (using OSCAR, composing workflows, ...)

On the [developer HowTo⁹](#) documentation, here are training materials for developers (linked in the training material catalogue). They are covering the following subjects:

- How to organize a tutorial,
- How to use the develop Dashboard
- How to configure storage providers

Timeline of the courses to be developed in the second part of the project:

Provided tutorial, based on the webinar series:

⁸ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/user/index.html#how-to-s>

⁹ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/technical/index.html#howto-s-developers>

[Introduction to AI4EOSC - for users](#)¹⁰

Future tutorials planned:

- AI4EOSC for developers”: Target developers of the AI services, 4Q 2024
- “Knowing the catalogue of services”, Target: EOSC researcher, Date: 4Q 2024
- “Composing AI Inference workflows based on OSCAR services with AI4Compose; Target: AI researcher, Date: 4Q 2024

3.4.2 IPR management

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) should be defined for each project result that could be protected with patents, copyright, design rights, database rights, trademarks, non-disclosure agreements, utility models and petty patents.

Services delivered on AI4EOSC project can be exploited by industrial partners to build their own machine learning and artificial intelligence applications having IPR setting for their own developments defined. Therefore, the IPR definition shall minimize the risk of IP-related service disruptions.

Undoubtedly, indicating participating partners' roles to set IPR definition according to their specific expertise and the foreground generated during the project activities is necessary.

Table 6. IPR project roles

KER	AI4EOSC Platform	AI4OS software stack	AI4EOSC Catalogue	AI4EOSC Exchange	AI4EOSC Models and technological solutions
Owner	joint-ownership by AI4EOSC Consortium, to be further discussed and agreed during project lifetime.	joint-ownership by AI4EOSC Consortium, to be further discussed and agreed during project lifetime.	joint-ownership by AI4EOSC Consortium, to be further discussed and agreed during project lifetime.	joint-ownership by AI4EOSC Consortium, to be further discussed and agreed during project lifetime.	joint-ownership by AI4EOSC Consortium, to be further discussed and agreed during project lifetime.
IPR approach	Project software based on open source licenses. Service offer does not require IP transfer.	Project software based on open source licenses. Service offer does not require IP transfer.	Project software based on open source licenses, other assets with CC-BY.	Offered with an open license. Consultancy as a service, no IP transfer.	Software tools that will be delivered in the portal are based on open source licenses.

¹⁰ <https://moodle.learn.eosc-synergy.eu/course/view.php?id=143>

3.4.3 Managing exploitation results

The project's outputs and related KERs will be fully defined during this last project phase and therefore exploitation opportunities will be assessed as part of the exploitation management. For each of the key assets, appropriate strategies will be defined for its exploitation.

As a consequence, a comprehensive set of activities for identified exploitation opportunities will be performed aiming at the effective exploitation of the project results. The WP2 responsible, in cooperation with all partners, will maintain and elaborate the final exploitation strategy plan in collaboration to develop an appropriate business plan(s).

3.5 MONITORING

The Lean Canvas method¹¹ was used as a basis to create the template used to depict KERs in [Section 2.2](#) *Exploitable results* and prepare the exploitation/business plan for a given exploitable result. Continuous updates to this adjusted form help to focus on problems, solutions, key metrics and competitive advantages.

¹¹ Maurya, A. (2010). Why Lean Canvas vs Business Model Canvas? Practice Trumps Theory.

4 DISSEMINATION PLAN

4.1 OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

This section describes a set of actions to ensure that the project's results are effectively communicated to relevant audiences, including other researchers, policymakers, and the general public.

The dissemination plan will outline the steps that will be taken to share the project's findings. It will involve identifying key target groups and developing a strategy to make these groups aware of the project's results and encourage adoption.

The dissemination plan for the AI4EOSC project has been implemented in three phases:

- I. **Launch campaign** (months 1-3): During this phase, the consortium has publicized the start of the project and its objectives, using the [project's website](#)¹², social media (such as X/[Twitter](#)¹³ and [YouTube](#)¹⁴), and other communication materials to generate interest and promote it among stakeholders e.g. partners local web pages. The consortium also developed visual identity and communication materials, such as brochures and posters, to create a consistent and cohesive brand for the project (see [Annex II](#) for further details).
- II. **Creation of awareness and engagement campaign** (months 3-15): During this phase, the consortium presents the approach to develop the platform and services to specialized audiences from the scientific community and industrial stakeholders, collecting feedback and further needs. This includes activities like organizing workshops and events where the project's results are being showcased and discussed with potential users and adopters. The consortium established potential partnerships with DIHs and SMEs, which will be involved in co-creation pilots to test and evaluate the project's results.
- III. **Promotion campaign** (months 15-36): This final phase focuses on promoting the project's results to relevant scientific and industry stakeholders, supporting the exploitation strategy of the project. The specifics of this promotion phase have been defined, based on the results of Tasks 2.1 and 2.2 and the identification of stakeholders. This involves

¹² <https://ai4eosc.eu/>

¹³ <https://twitter.com/AI4EOSC>

¹⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/@ai4eosc>

using a wide range of strategies, from publishing articles in relevant scientific journals and presenting at conferences and workshops, to promoting the project's results and engaging with potential adopters. The consortium uses social media and other online platforms (such as the EOSC Forum or the EOSC association newsletters) to reach a wider audience and increase awareness of the project's results. In addition AI4EOSC organize cyclic Open Calls for new use cases to become adopters of the platform, participating in the evaluation and co-design of the platform.

To maximize the impact of the project's dissemination material for end users, the AI4EOSC project will prioritize the translation of selected key resources into national languages. This will ensure that the project's information and resources are accessible to a wider audience, including those who may not speak English as their first language.

4.2 TARGET AUDIENCE

The AI4EOSC project has identified several target groups that it will aim to reach and engage with through its dissemination strategy and liaisons. These target groups are described below.

- **Research communities:** The project aims to motivate the research community to engage with the EOSC initiatives and the new services and functionalities developed within the project. This could include researchers working in various fields, such as agriculture, biomedicine, and energy, who are especially interested in finding new ways to use AI/ML/DL tools and services more effectively.
- **AI/ML/DL practitioners and application developers:** The project aims to raise awareness of the availability of AI/ML/DL tools and services in the EOSC ecosystem and encourage their adoption by practitioners and developers working in these fields. This could include data scientists, machine learning engineers, and software developers who are looking for ways to build and deploy AI/ML/DL applications at scale.
- **Similar technological platforms and initiatives:** The project aims to promote interoperability and establish partnerships/liaisons with other platforms and initiatives (e.g. AI4Europe and the AI-on-Demand Platform) that offer similar services and also with service providers promoting easy installation and integration on the platform.
- **The EOSC ecosystem:** The project aims to raise awareness of the integration and availability of AI/ML/DL services in the EOSC portal and

promote the AI4EOSC exchange with existing applications. This could include stakeholders within the EOSC ecosystem, such as service providers, data managers, and researchers, who are looking for ways to more effectively use and benefit from the EOSC (e.g. TF Technical Interoperability of Data and Services). In addition project members participate in relevant EOSC Task Forces to promote the technologies and results of the project in EOSC.

- **Other projects exploiting AI solutions:** AI4EOSC strives to foster additional collaborations with ongoing initiatives leveraging AI solutions, like iMagine (AI-based image tools for aquatic sciences) or FlexiGroBots (AI for intelligent automation of precision agriculture) EU projects.
- **Education:** The project aims to integrate AI4EOSC knowledge and solutions into data science curricula and courses. This could include educators and students who are interested in learning about the latest developments in AI/ML/DL and how to apply these technologies in their work.
- **Digital innovation Hubs (DIHs):** The project aims to extend the DIHs' portfolio of offers with AI4EOSC services and consultancy, and establish new collaborations through this channel. This could include DIHs that are looking for ways to offer new AI/ML/DL services to their customers and partners.
- **SMEs, innovators, startups:** The project aims to foster the uptake of the project's products by these groups, to support the exploitation of the project's use cases. This could include small and medium-sized enterprises, innovators, and startups who are looking for ways to incorporate AI/ML/DL technologies into their products and services.
- **General public and the media:** The project also aims at reaching the broader society via the media and will try to establish solid ties with both specialized and generalist media.

Following a segmented approach presented, a tailored set of actions are defined to follow specific dissemination strategies for each of the target audiences. These strategies are presented below.

To engage with **research communities** and **AI/ML/DL practitioners** and **application developers**, the AI4EOSC project has established a comprehensive set of case studies that demonstrate the successful use of the resources developed by the project. These [case studies](https://ai4eosc.eu/use-cases/)¹⁵ are featured on the project's

¹⁵ <https://ai4eosc.eu/use-cases/>

website and will serve as a key component of our dissemination and communication efforts, including social media campaigns, webinars, and events. Those success stories will present both the internal project use cases as well as supported external cases.

The case studies provide concrete examples of how researchers can benefit from using the resources developed by EOSC, as well as how service providers can directly benefit from offering services and resources through the former EOSC portal. To further showcase the capabilities of the AI4EOSC platform, the project provides demonstrations of the platform at relevant workshops and will generate showcases for various domains. These efforts help to highlight the value and potential of the AI4EOSC resources to research communities and AI/ML/DL practitioners and application developers. Such activities have been intensified in particular after the release of the AI4EOSC Platform and with the new web page design that is focused on promoting the products and services.

To engage with **similar technological platforms**, the consortium established direct contacts with relevant platforms and sought to share knowledge and identify common points of collaboration (e.g. EOSC ecosystem, or AI-on-demand). This involves actively seeking out opportunities to engage with these platforms and establish partnerships that can help to promote interoperability and facilitate the exchange of ideas and resources. By establishing these relationships and fostering collaboration, the project aims to increase the reach and impact of its resources and contribute to the development of the broader AI/ML/DL ecosystem.

The AI4EOSC project coordinates its dissemination efforts with the communication teams of **EOSC-related initiatives** (e.g. EOSC Association, EOSC Future in the previous reporting period and its follow-ups like EOSC-Beyond and the EOSC Focus projects among others) in order to engage with the EOSC ecosystem. One of the channels of such activities is the created working group on the EOSC Focus Communication and Engagement WG. Through these partnerships, the project is able to disseminate its results and updates through the existing communication channels of these initiatives, including social media, the EOSC Forum community updates, events, and news. This coordinated approach will help to ensure that the project's information and resources are directly shared with the EOSC ecosystem and can be accessed by stakeholders within the ecosystem, such as service providers, data managers, and researchers.

The project aims to engage with the **Education** audience by making direct contact with universities and participating in selected educational events. This includes establishing partnerships with institutions that offer relevant courses (e.g.

[Master in Data Science UC/UIMP¹⁶](#) or an [Introduction to Data Science course FIIT STU¹⁷](#)) and collaborating with educators to integrate AI4EOSC knowledge and solutions into their curricula. In addition, the project will invite relevant stakeholders from the Education sector to participate in its advisory board, providing a platform for ongoing dialogue and collaboration. By engaging in these ways, the project hopes to promote the adoption of AI/ML/DL technologies in education and to support the next generation of data scientists and AI practitioners.

Regarding **Digital Innovation Hubs** (DIHs), the AI4EOSC project aimed at establishing collaborations and partnerships with relevant DIHs (e.g EOSC DIH - described in next section) and clusters through existing links with project partners. This strategy is intended to make the projects' services and consultancy offerings available to DIHs and to encourage the adoption and integration of these resources into their portfolio of offerings.

Finally, in order to foster the uptake of the different products developed by AI4EOSC among **SME, innovators and startups**, our communication efforts will be targeted toward these groups, with a focus in disseminating the use-cases developed by the project partners through events and webinars specific use-cases sectors. Other actions include engaging with projects and hubs such as European Lab for Learning and Intelligent Systems (ELLIS) to gain visibility among their members, and leveraging the established network of collaboration switch DIHs to multiply the impact of the outreach efforts outreach potential interested parties. These efforts will be aimed at raising awareness of AI4EOSC products and encouraging their adoption by SME, innovators and startups. After the first release, we plan to prepare a series of open calls for external use cases (also for SME, innovators and startups) to exploit particular aspects of the platform in different domains. Currently, there are initial discussions on the calls organization that would allow to maximize the impact. The project is going to leverage the experience coming from the EOSC DIH calls for interests and open calls.

4.3 ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

It should be noted that all members of the consortium are involved to a greater or lesser extent in the tasks related to the impact of the project. The Work Package (WP) leader is PSNC.

¹⁶ <https://masterdatascience.ifca.es/>

¹⁷ <https://github.com/FIIT-IAU/2021-2022>

All partners are open to collaborating and participating in any dissemination task, but different partners will be responsible for coordinating the efforts for each task.

- CSIC acts as the moderator of the AI4EOSC Project social media profiles, controlling and filtering content and monitoring the impact of the information uploaded.
- The website was initially developed and maintained by Predictia, updating the website pages with the latest events and news, with an update during the second half of the project, focused on maximizing the project market potential.

However, given that the information to be communicated can come from all partner institutions, it is necessary that all partners contribute to the social media and website effort and provide input.

4.4 REPORT ON THE ACTIVITIES

4.4.1 European Commission coordination meetings

AI4EOSC has actively participated in the Coordination meetings of the EOSC-related projects organized by the European Commission in 2022, 2023 and 2024. There have been 3 different meetings so far: September 2022, June 2023, and June 2024; all of them in Brussels. Project representatives (project coordinator and the WP2 leader) presented AI4EOSC (1st meeting), its contributions to the SRIA (2nd meeting) and the integration of the project's outcomes in the wider EOSC federation (3rd meeting).

Those events have been very successful in terms of establishing a network of collaboration with other projects from the INFRAEOSC ecosystem, as described in what follows:

- [RAISE](https://raise-science.eu/)¹⁸: A set of common meetings were carried out, establishing some collaboration points at the technical level. This collaboration is ongoing towards the federation of different project solutions at both sides.
- [FAIR-EASE](https://fairease.eu/)¹⁹: An initial scouting of commonalities have been carried out at project coordination level.
- [FAIR-IMPACT](https://fair-impact.eu/)²⁰: AI4EOSC has participated in the FAIR-IMPACT open call for support, without success. We are now engaging more closely with the

¹⁸ <https://raise-science.eu/>

¹⁹ <https://fairease.eu/>

²⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/>

FAIR-IMPACT project through participation in the FAIR-IMPACT synchronization workshops held in 2023 and 2024.

- [BlueCloud2026](#)²¹: An initial scouting of commonalities have been carried out at project coordination level. Some potential federation and interoperability activities have been initially identified and will be followed up during the last phase of the project.
- [Skills4EOSC](#)²²: We have participated in the Delphi study on FAIR in ML/AI conducted by the Skills4EOSC project. Moreover, one of our researchers has been awarded a "Joining a Host Institution's Project" grant from the SKILL4EOSC fellowship program, with the aim of collaborating with KIT (Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, SKILLS4EOSC partner), within the context of EOSC in various areas, such as the use of repositories for hosting and reusing research data for different purposes, as well as the development of training plans in data management, including their exploitation and processing on platforms such as AI4EOSC.
- [FAIRCORE4EOSC](#)²³: We have identified a potential collaboration in terms of early adopters of some of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components in order to contribute our metadata schemas and crosswalks to the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR). Further activities will be carried out during Q4 2024, when the AI4EOSC metadata system is mature enough.

More details on the ongoing collaboration activities are provided in the next section, including collaborations within the EOSC ecosystem and beyond.

[4.4.2 Collaboration with INFRAEOSC projects](#)

[BlueCloud2026](#)

Blue-Cloud 2026 is a collaborative project that leverages Europe's expertise in aquatic environmental observation and data handling. Building on existing infrastructures like Copernicus and EMODnet, Blue-Cloud aims to create a federated ecosystem for FAIR and open data in marine research. Through a web-based platform, it offers simplified access to multidisciplinary datasets, analytical services, and computing facilities.

Overall, the global objective of collaboration between AI4EOSC and the BlueCloud is to find some way of federation between the BlueCloud platform (based on

²¹ <https://blue-cloud.org/>

²² <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/>

²³ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

D4Science) and AI4EOSC, so that BlueCloud users can exploit AI4EOSC to build AI applications, with access to their BlueCloud environment and existing data.

In this context, we are evaluating the best approach to make both Authentication and Authorization systems and identities compatible. AI4EOSC and BlueCloud2025 will federate with BlueCloud AAI and create a dedicated namespace (internal to AI4EOSC platform) so that AI4EOSC can partition resources for BlueCloud users, allowing also to give access to a BlueCloud space from the AI4EOSC platform.

RAISE

The EU-funded RAISE project aims to provide the mechanisms for a distributed crowdsourced data processing system, moving from open data to data open for processing. To do so, RAISE will attempt to adapt open data to the culture of the research community, ensuring FAIR principles, defined as findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability. Project work includes the delivery of a cloud platform to coordinate the data sourcing and sharing process as well as a synthetic data generator.

AI4EOSC and RAISE would like to join forces to provide scientists and EOSC users of both platforms with a seamless environment to analyse sensitive data as available in the RAISE nodes through the AI4EOSC platform. In this context both projects will explore the federation of the two platforms so that users can get access to exemplary or synthetic datasets (from RAISE) within the AI4EOSC platform in order to develop AI applications that can be then submitted to the RAISE platform for execution over original data.

The preliminary plan includes the utilization of the AI4EOSC interactive environments (Jupyter Lab and Visual Studio Code) for RAISE users in order to provide them with tools for algorithm development with access to synthetic, anonymised or small versions of controlled dataset coming from the RAISE platform. In this context, RAISE provides access to these datasets via the RAISE Portal and RAISE nodes, and AI4EOSC has the ability to pre-download and sync data in user execution environments.

Collaboration with EOSC Association and EOSC-Focus project

AI4EOSC representatives participate in the EOSC Forum, which was created to facilitate the exchange of information and the collaboration between EOSC projects, as well as the coordination of the calendar of the events.

Most of the coordination activities carried out by the association are being covered by the EOSC-Focus project, as described in what follows.

Contributions to the EOSC Macro Roadmap

The EOSC-Focus has developed a macro roadmap towards the building of the EOSC and the implementation of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), including results and contributions from all the relevant EOSC stakeholders: EOSC Association members, national initiatives and INFRAEOSC projects. In this context, AI4EOSC has provided input and feedback to the Macro Roadmap team, creating [dedicated content](#)²⁴ on our webpage for each of the AI4EOSC entries.

Working Groups meetings

The EOSC-Focus project has set up a set of working groups (WG), where AI4EOSC is actively engaged, namely:

- **HE Communication and Engagement WG.** The Horizon Europe Communication and Engagement Working Group has its monthly meetings (around 20 meetings so far) and a dedicated channel on EOSC Forum. During the meetings, projects have opportunities to discuss specific topics to align and collaborate on stakeholder engagement and communication activities.
 - AI4EOSC is represented in this working group by the WP2 leader.
 - AI4EOSC provided input for the initial group general presentation.
 - AI4EOSC provides cyclic updates of the activities and major news.
 - Other discussed subjects:
 - EOSC Symposium preparations.
 - Macro-roadmap.
 - Events calendar synchronization.
 - EOSC & Dataspaces webinar.
 - Major news and collaboration opportunities from projects.
- **HE Impact WG.** This group focuses on discussing EOSC's current developments and fostering synergies and productive collaborations. During the meetings, projects have opportunities to discuss the impact of the project and sustainability.
 - AI4EOSC is represented in this working group by the WP2 leader.
 - AI4EOSC participated in the group during Winter School, and joined some of the group meetings, where AI4EOSC were taken as an

²⁴ <https://ai4eosc.eu/sria/>

- example of the exploitation of the results planning, shown to other projects
- AI4EOSC provided feedback for the tools/forms to collect/plan the impact by the projects
 - **HE Technology WG:** AI4EOSC continues to participate in the Horizon Europe Technology Working Group (on a monthly basis), coordinated by the EOSC Focus project. In the meetings, all the technical coordinators of the different Horizon Europe EOSC-related projects collaborate to foster cross-project collaboration and engagement. AI4EOSC is represented in this working group by the WP3 leader. From this participation we can highlight the following activities:
 - EOSC Winter School: the AI4EOSC members participated in the first edition of this event, celebrated in January 2024 (Thessaloniki, Greece). The main purpose of the event was to gather relevant technical staff from Horizon Europe EOSC-related projects that can potentially find commonalities and establish fruitful collaborations between projects. Currently, the preparations for the 2025 EOSC Winter School are ongoing, and it is expected from AI4EOSC to participate in this new edition.
 - Collaboration between AI4EOSC and RAISE projects: coming from the EOSC Winter School, we have formally established a collaboration between projects, as described above in this document.
 - Participation in the Opportunity Area 4 (OA4) “User & Resource Environments”: as a derived activity coming also from the EOSC Winter School, the AI4EOSC WP3 leader is participating in the OA4 Expert group, coordinated by EOSC Focus. Currently, in the monthly meetings of this group, we are preparing for the EOSC symposium (21-23 October, Berlin (Germany)), where there will be a dedicated session on INFRAEOSC projects.

4.4.3 Other EU funded project collaborations

AI4EOSC has established a set of collaborations with other EU funded projects and initiatives beyond the EOSC ecosystem, as detailed in what follows.

iImagine

The [iImagine](https://www.imagine-ai.eu/)²⁵ is a Horizon Europe-funded project under the call HORIZON-INFRA-2021-SERV-01-06. This project is focused on delivering an AI platform in

²⁵<https://www.imagine-ai.eu/>

order to exploit imaging assets for aquatic science, targeting relevant user communities and Research Infrastructures. iImagine is exploiting the services that were provided by the DEEP-Hybrid-DataCloud project through the EOSC marketplace, which are now superseded by the AI4EOSC and AI4OS software stack. In this regard, iImagine has deployed a customized platform based on the AI4OS software, accessible through a [dedicated dashboard](#)²⁶, with dedicated resources, but remaining compatible with the AI4EOSC platform.

The screenshot displays the iImagine marketplace interface for the 'Phytoplankton species classifier (VLIZ)'. The page includes a sidebar with navigation links, a main content area with detailed information about the classifier (including its purpose, provider, and categories), and a section for user options and references. The classifier is described as an application for identifying plankton species, developed by VLIZ (Flanders Marine Institute). It is categorized as a Docker-based, TensorFlow-powered, deep learning application, which is pretrained, transferable, and used for image classification via Jupyter. The dashboard also provides links to GitHub, Report issue, Dataset, and Dockerhub.

Figure 2. Screenshot of iImagine dashboard, based on the AI4EOSC

AI4EOSC is incorporating user feedback from iImagine communities into its development roadmap, resulting in an exceptional situation to enrich and improve the platform with features requested outside the AI4EOSC activities.

AI4Life

[AI4Life](#)²⁷ is a Horizon Europe-funded project under the call HORIZON-INFRA-2021-SERV-01-06, that brings together the computational and life science communities. Its goal is to empower life science researchers to harness the full potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) methods for bioimage analysis, particularly microscopy image analysis, by providing services, and developing standards aimed at both developers and users. AI4Life promises to create harmonized and interoperable AI tools & methods via open calls and public challenges and bring these developments to researchers via strategic outreach and advanced training. The services provided and solutions developed within the AI4Life framework are crucial to solving today's microscopy image

²⁶ <https://dashboard.cloud.imagine-ai.eu/>

²⁷ <https://ai4life.eurobioimaging.eu/>

analysis problems and will contribute to boosting the pace of biological and medical insights and discovery in the coming years.

A collaboration has been started in terms of access to the AI4EOOSC platform and resources and its marketplace. In this context we have established a [customized version](#)²⁸ of the platform and dashboard for the AI4Life collaboration in order to allow them to use a restricted amount of resources in our platform. We will additionally explore making it possible to download AI4Life datasets through the AI4EOOSC external datasets integration and allowing AI4Life users to deploy their models in the marketplace.

AI-on-Demand/AI4EU

AI4Europe project goal is to manage, develop and facilitate the AI-on-Demand Platform (AIoD).

AI4Europe has developed services like the AIoD Marketplace or the AIoD Catalogue. AI4EOOSC established early in the project the collaboration with AI4Europe regarding the AioD planned architecture, the good practices, the standards regarding the resources description. A series of the meetings took place between representatives of both initiatives. As a result of collaboration with AI4EOOSC, AIoD uses the AI4OS "AI4 Dashboard" project as a base for its own dashboard²⁹. Some functionalities have been adapted to AIoD's purposes. Besides, AI4EOOSC is working on crosswalks between different metadata formats, in order to make it possible to easily translate metadata from one platform to the other.

Figure 3. Screenshot of AI on Demand dashboard, based on the AI4EOOSC.

²⁸ <https://ai4life.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/>

²⁹ <https://github.com/aiondemand/AIOD-marketplace-frontend>

European AI Security Network (EASiNet)

The European AI Security Network (EASiNet) brings together several European funded projects to collaborate on AI and cybersecurity in different fields. The main goal is to raise awareness, exchange project results, promote open science, and develop common strategies for project exploitation. In particular, this network aims to collaborate in addressing critical issues in the intersection of AI and cybersecurity.

The projects that are currently involved in these network are: AI4EOSC, CERTIFY, ENCRYPT, EOSC-TITAN, FLUTE, HARPOCRATES, KATCHY, ONCOVALUE, PAROMA-MED, TRUMPET, WARIFA.

Among the main activities, in addition to the organization of various meetings to establish synergies and collaboration channels, the most important contribution is the organization of a one-day event as a crosstalk workshop with the aim of enabling each participant project to present a contribution or solution to an specific track, including Cloud Security for data,

Privacy Enhancement Technologies and Federated Learning adoption and related certification in the medical data scenario. In addition, some authorities involved in policy creation will be invited to this event which will be held in Brussels on October 22. From AI4EOSC, we have actively participated in the scientific organization of this event, being part of the scientific committee, and we will contribute with a lecture included in the track concerning cloud security for data.

4.4.4 Other collaborations

Flower.ai

[Flower](https://flower.ai/)³⁰ is a widely used framework within both the industry and the scientific community for Federated Learning. Within WP4, one of the main objectives (framed in Task 4.4) is to support building AI systems on distributed datasets, with a particular focus on federated learning. In this regard, after carrying out an extensive review of the state of the art concerning Python based FL frameworks, Flower emerged as the most compelling choice for integration into the AI4EOSC platform.

Collaboration with the developers of this software is a quite important milestone

³⁰ <https://flower.ai/>

we have accomplished over the last year. This collaboration has been made effective in different ways:

- We were invited to participate in an online workshop as part of their “Flower Monthly” series. This talk took place on January 3, 2024, and it was entitled [“Federated Learning with Flower in the European Open Science Cloud”](#)³¹. In this talk we presented the EOSC ecosystem, the AI4EOSC project and the implementation of the FL architecture within the platform, and a use case of federated learning application to environmental sciences and water quality.
- We were invited to participate in the Flower Summit 2024, which is the world's largest FL conference and which was held in London on March 14-15, 2024. We contributed to this event with a talk entitled [“Federating AI in the European Open Science Cloud”](#)³², in which we introduced the EOSC ecosystem, presented the AI4EOSC project, talked about how we have implemented Federated Learning in the AI4EOSC platform and exposed the AI4EOSC approach for allowing client authentication in FL.
- In terms of software development, we have contributed to Flower in two ways. The first one, resolving an issue that affected the connection after a reverse proxy, so that the pull request submitted by AI4EOSC was accepted and our solution was integrated into Flower. The second is by developing an extension to Flower that is used in the AI4EOSC to allow clients to authenticate using a token to participate in a FL training.
- Within the framework of the webinar series organized by AI4EOSC, the third of them had as topic Federated Learning (April 22, 2024). In it, the Flower team was invited to contribute with a talk about this software, entitled [“Flower: a friendly federated learning framework”](#)³³ and given by Javier Fernandez-Marques from FlowerLabs.

NVFLARE and Monai

[NVFlare](#)³⁴ is the NVIDIA Federated Learning³⁴ Application Runtime Environment, and it is a business-ready Python FL framework.

The collaboration with NVFlare has been developed in the context of working meetings to explore the possibility of integrating this software into the AI4EOSC platform in addition to Flower. This is currently work in progress. Regarding

³¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RRtfRPQBAdo&t=1s>

³² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IJUbc822fSI>

³³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=v7blpOB92C8>

³⁴ <https://github.com/NVIDIA/NVFlare>

software development, AI4EOSC has made a pull request for integrating in NVFLARE two new aggregation functions for TensorFlow which has been accepted by the NVFLARE team.

[MONAI](https://monai.io/index.html)³⁵ is a set of open-source, freely available collaborative frameworks built for accelerating research and clinical collaboration in Medical Imaging. In addition, MONAI has a specific working group for Federated Learning and Applications. In collaboration with this working group (involving researchers from NVIDIA-NVFLARE), we held an online talk introducing AI4EOSC and our approach for implementing FL within the platform on April 10, 2024.

4.4.5 External engagement and involvement

Open calls for additional use cases

AI4EOSC, after the first platform release, has organized an open call to attract applications for new use cases that want to accelerate their AI model development in the EOSC. The goal is to onboard researchers, businesses and innovators developing innovative solutions and help them improve their products and services by taking advantage of AI/ML/DL technologies and models within the EOSC.

The selected pilots have been offered with support in, among other areas:

- Using the production AI4EOSC platform, with early access to preview of new and experimental features;
- Accessing EOSC e-infrastructure resources and additional technical services;
- Prototyping, scaling up, design, performance verification and testing;
- Building partnerships with other partners, SMEs and the ecosystem;

The call was targeted towards Research organizations, researchers, start-ups, spin-offs or, SMEs from EU countries (eligible to HE), provided that they were willing to develop solutions using different AI4EOSC services (with a priority on federated learning) and contributing to the AI4EOSC catalog of modules (<https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu> and <https://github.com/ai4os-hub/>) and the wider EOSC, FAIR and open data ecosystem.

The results of the call are the following. Five proposals were received. After evaluating its technical details, maturity level, resources requested, impact, four were accepted and one rejected.

³⁵ <https://monai.io/index.html>

These are the institutions that have submitted proposals for the First AI4EOSC Open Call:

- **Title of the proposal:** Reconstructing three dimensional salinity and temperature fields from surface satellite observations and in-situ ARGO profiles.
 - **Affiliation:** [Institut Ciències del Mar](#)³⁶ - Spanish National Research Council (ICM-CSIC)
 - **Entity description:** The ICM conducts frontier research and fosters both knowledge and technology transfer on topics related to ocean and climate interactions, conservation and sustainable use of marine life and ecosystems, and impact mitigation of natural and anthropogenic hazards
- **Title of the proposal:** Plant identification on high-resolution mosaics of drone imagery: Mediterranean shrubs and tropical palms
 - **Affiliation:** [Geociencias Barcelona](#)³⁷ - Spanish National Research Council (GEO3BCN-CSIC)
 - **Entity description:** GEO3BCN, part of the Spanish National Research Council CSIC, conducts cutting-edge research in various fields of geosciences, including: Seismic studies, Geothermal energy, Volcanology, Geochemical carbon dioxide removal among many other activities.
- **Title of the proposal:** AI Model for Cracks Detection in Agnostic Environment
 - **Affiliation:** [Vertliner](#)³⁸ - VERTLINER is a field robotics company, developing autonomous robotic aerial platforms for the indoor assessment of assets.
 - **Entity description:** Vertliner is a field-robotics startup that focuses on developing autonomous robotic systems for the precise indoor assessment of building assets.
- **Title of the proposal:** Data fusion based on Machine Learning to increase spectral and spatial resolution in Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3
 - **Affiliation:** [Institute of Marine Sciences of Andalusia](#)³⁹ - Spanish National Research Council (ICMAN-CSIC); [Institute of Physics of Cantabria](#)⁴⁰ - Spanish National Research Council (IFCA-CSIC)

³⁶ <https://bec.icm.csic.es/>

³⁷ <https://www.geo3bcn.csic.es/>

³⁸ <https://vertliner.com/>

³⁹ <https://www.icman.csic.es/>

⁴⁰ <https://ifca.unican.es/en-us>

- **Entity description:** The Institute of Marine Sciences of Andalusia (ICMAN), part of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), is dedicated to advancing marine science research.
- **Title of the proposal:** Innovative Marine Resource and Habitat Analysis
 - **Affiliation:** [Havforskningsinstituttet](#)⁴¹ (IMR)
 - **Entity description:** Is one of the largest marine research institutes in Europe, headquartered in Bergen, Norway. It plays a crucial role in marine science and sustainable management of marine resources

Collaboration with EOSC DIH

A formal collaboration with EOSC DIH was established at the beginning of the AI4EOSC project. EOSC DIH is a community of over 70 companies currently in the EOSC Ecosystem, providing the opportunity to engage with the private sector. Many of those companies are delivering the services based on the AI, being a good target community and link for the AI4EOSC. The main tasks of the collaboration include:

- Identification of the AI4EOSC services that can be offered to SMEs and those to be included in the [EOSC DIH offering/portfolio](#)⁴².
- Agreement on the detailed support mechanism through the EOSC DIH pilots for the SMEs using AI4EOSC services.
- Collaboration to define common business pilots.
- Identify ways the open calls or campaigns published by both parties can realise synergies.
- EOSC DIH will contribute to promoting the AI4EOSC services through the current EOSC DIH community.
- Both entities will collaborate in terms of mutual dissemination activities.

AI4EOSC has been used as an example promoted also during the EOSC DIH community meeting (general presentation and a presentation of the services).

As a result AI4EOSC is supporting pilots in collaboration with EOSC DIH, providing the expertise, services and limited resources:

- **EOSC DIH AWARE Pilot (Aero Waste Assessment with the use of Robotics Equipment)** AWARE pilot, leverages a semi-autonomous UAV equipped with advanced sensor modalities. This software's purpose is to detect materials frequently seen on construction sites. By identifying these

⁴¹ <https://hi.no/hi/en>

⁴² <https://eosc-dih.eu/list-of-all-services/>

materials, we aim to significantly improve waste management processes. VERTLINER is developing aerial robotic platforms to improve waste management in indoor construction sites. Their UAVs detect and categorize waste using advanced sensors, producing rich data that could be subject to train neural-based powerful AI models provided through EOSC DIH's and collaborating projects - AI services and computing resources.

VERTLINER is a pioneering field robotics company specializing in the creation of autonomous robotic aerial platforms for indoor asset assessments. Through the use of High-Performance Computing (HPC) services, the AWARE pilot seeks to harness the power of AI by training a Neural Network. This will enable the company to develop an efficient AI model for accurate material detection, ultimately enhancing VERTLINER's information gathering capabilities regarding objects in areas of interest.

Following the development phase, this AI model will be seamlessly integrated into VERTLINER's advanced aerial platforms. Field tests will be conducted in actual construction settings, validating the model's performance and reliability. Post-testing, we're committed to making iterative enhancements, drawing from invaluable data insights and on-the-ground feedback, ensuring the continual advancement of our solution. AI4EOSC, as a supporting project in this pilot, provides the platform for testing, resources and expertise to support the use case.

- **EOSC DIH REGREEN** as well as EOSC DIH Mradsimide pilots, it has also been evaluating the usage of the AI4EOSC services, and several interactions took place, to present the services and capabilities. Mradsimide pilot has been evaluating the training services.

Branding - adjusting

Apart from the initial co-branding that AI4EOSC adopted already in previous reporting periods, AI4EOSC has adopted the starter kit offered by the EOSC-Focus project for our project image, in order to be able to provide a more coherent vision of the graphical materials with respect to the EOSC.

Moreover, there were 2 redesigns of the project webpage: one beginning of 2024, and another related to changing the scope of the webpage into the product/services that took place between May-August 2024 .

4.4.6 Scientific Publications

In the recent period project members continued to be very active in the publication of the initial results of the project, which resulted in 16 publications.

These were published in several journals and conferences, such as the Water research, Future Generation Computer Systems, Earth Sciences Informatics, Procedia Computer Science, Automation in Construction, CEUR Workshop, Information Hiding and Multimedia Security 2024 (IH&MMSEC). More information is presented in Annex V. In addition, this information is being captured and monitored on our [internal confluence pages](#)⁴³, and available as well as other information on the [AI4EOSC Zenodo repository](#)⁴⁴.

4.4.7 Relevant workshop participation

AI session and workshop at EGI'2023

AI4EOSC partners had a rich program during the EGI 2023 conference, organized at PSNC, Poznan, Poland on June 19-13, 2023. The project is the co-organizer of the session “Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in distributed/federated environments” at the conference, where it had four presentations: “Empowering EOSC scientists with AI services and tools”, “Distributed computing platform on EGI Federated Cloud”, “MLOps platforms review: case study for AI4EOSC”, and “DEEPaaS API: The Community API for AI in the EOSC”. AI4EOSC also organized the hands-on workshop “Training: Bringing your AI models to EOSC”, where AI practitioners and all interested people learned how the AI4EOSC/DEEP AI platform supports typical scenarios for AI-based applications and services: re-use of existing AI modules on the marketplace, AI model development from scratch and training, and model serving. The training session was also streamed online and recorded videos are available for partners in the AI4EOSC but also in the iImagine projects.

Websites for programs:

- [“Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in distributed/federated environments”](#)⁴⁵ session
- [“Bringing your AI models to EOSC”](#)⁴⁶ workshop:

There were more than 20 participants attending the session, either in person or online.

⁴³ <https://confluence.ifca.es/display/AI4/Peer-reviewed+publications+table>

⁴⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/ai4eosc/search?page=1&size=20>

⁴⁵ <https://whova.com/web/M8zkrnLo5DUwlnug54VINPkHTdssyl49PHa20jCW2Qg%3D/Agenda/>

⁴⁶ <https://whova.com/web/M8zkrnLo5DUwlnug54VINPkHTdssyl49PHa20jCW2Qg%3D/Agenda/>

AI4EOSC Platform: User's workshop

A [two-day workshop](#)⁴⁷ for bringing AI4EOSC platform users, supporters, and developers together to share their experiences and upcoming updates of the platform is scheduled at IISAS, Bratislava, Slovakia on November 15-16, 2023. People working on use cases presented their current status and challenges, and worked together with platform developers on solving existing issues. The workshop also provided opportunities for platform developers to present current status and expected new features of the platform to existing users from AI4EOSC as well as iMagine projects, and also to external participants who are interested in using the platform.

AI4EOSC Platform: Online workshops

In addition 3 online workshops and training introducing the AI4EOSC platform have been prepared and conducted during 2024.

In these 3 workshops⁴⁸, we have provided (1) a comprehensive overview of AI and Machine Learning (ML) technologies together with an introduction to the

⁴⁷ <https://indico.scc.kit.edu/event/3845/timetable/#20231115>

⁴⁸ <https://indico.ifca.es/category/54/>

platform⁴⁹, provided a specialized session in image processing using AI techniques⁵⁰, concluding with an introduction with federated learning⁵¹. The workshops targeted researchers that work with AI or are new to the field as these workshops offered valuable insights and practical guidance for harnessing the power of AI within the EOSC ecosystem.

- **Online Workshop 1: Introduction to the platform (March 2024)**

In this first session, [Introduction to the platform](#)⁵², we provided a comprehensive overview of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) technologies, going into the capabilities of AI4EOSC, and guided users through using the platform's dashboard for seamless data analysis and module development. The workshop has been attended in total by more than 400 users (with around 150 following the live stream)

- **Online Workshop 2: Image processing with AI4EOSC (April 2024)**

The second of our workshop series, focusing on [Image processing with AI4EOSC](#)⁵³. It dived into the exciting realm of image analysis and enhancement with the AI4EOSC platform, focusing on techniques for leveraging artificial intelligence (AI) to extract valuable insights from visual data. From image segmentation to superresolution, this workshop offered a comprehensive overview of advanced AI techniques and their applications within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem. The workshop has been attended in total by over 250 users (around 100 users following the live stream).

- **Online Workshop 3: Introduction to federated learning (April 2024)**

In [Introduction to Federated Learning](#)⁵⁴, we unraveled the potential of this cutting-edge approach in distributed machine learning. Across four dynamic sessions, we covered everything from the basics and best practices to understanding threats and exploring friendly frameworks like Flower. We presented applications within the AI4EOSC platform through live demonstrations and engaging discussions. The workshop has been attended in total by over 250 users (around 80 users following the live stream).

⁴⁹ <https://indico.ifca.es/event/3131/>

⁵⁰ <https://indico.ifca.es/event/3133/>

⁵¹ <https://indico.ifca.es/event/3134/>

⁵² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=op70toJFBrk>

⁵³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JQOWmsEQANs>

⁵⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=v7blpOB92C8>

4.5 INSTRUMENTS AND CHANNELS

4.5.1 Website and its evolution

The AI4EOOSC project website, hosted on ai4eoosc.eu, serves as a central hub for the dissemination of information about our project and the work that we are doing to develop and provide advanced Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, and Deep Learning services to the research community through the European Open Science Cloud. The website will also develop a section for training materials.

Figure 4. Screenshot of AI4EOOSC project's landing web page.

On the website, you can access information about the partners, goals and objectives of the AI4EOOSC project, as well as stay up-to-date with the latest events and news related to AI4EOOSC. You can also access all deliverables, scientific publications and branding materials. Besides, it features three selected use cases, access to the AI4EOOSC platform and the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda. The whole website went through a redesign process in order to make it more accessible and intuitive.

The expansion of the website was done drawing from partners' comments, and a "Designed for" section was added on the main page to showcase the different

stakeholders and segments of the population who could become potential users of the AI4EOSC services.

A timeline was added too, for stakeholders to monitor progress and understand at what stage the project is.

The redesign also tried to make it more visually-engaging while respecting the branding guidelines and the project's visual identity.

As already stated, we are working on a complete redesign of the webpage through the services of a professional web designer, in order to better organize the information and provide a more impactful experience, aligned with the EOSC co-branding guidelines. We expect to release the new web page in October 2024.

4.5.2 Website metrics and news/blogs

As of October 2023 [M13 of AI4EOSC], 9 stories had been published in the [News section](#).⁵⁵ So far, the section received input from several partners whenever there were newsworthy meetings, congresses or events, and it's updated regularly, but it relies heavily on an all-partners collaboration and needs to be sustained throughout the project.

Since the records began in April 2024, the website has registered more than 6000 unique users with more than 30000 views, almost half of them accessing the website directly. A third of the remaining ones access the website via organic search.

4.5.3 Social networks

Social media has undoubtedly become one of the most important tools people resort to in order to find and/or spread information – from average citizens or private companies to government officials or institutions. It's a powerful tool to reach out to specialized sectors too, and media increasingly use it as a source.

In addition to serving as a tool for communication and dissemination, our social media presence would allow us to build a community of followers and engage in dialogue with stakeholders.

The AI4EOSC Project is regularly using X/Twitter and YouTube (the Mastodon is inactive). In [Section 3.5](#), a list of Key Performance Indicators is proposed for monitoring the different social media networks (see Table 2).

⁵⁵ <https://ai4eosc.eu/events-media/news/>

Twitter ([@AI4EOSC](https://twitter.com/AI4EOSC)⁵⁶)

The use of Twitter will be focused on communicating AI4EOSC news, events, calls and partners activity. Suggested hashtag for all the pieces of information: **#AI4EOSC**

Mastodon (mastodon.social/@ai4eosc⁵⁷)

It's still at an early stage, but it was investigated as a complementary tool to expand the reach of the Twitter account. For the moment the account is inactive. More explanation is being done in the monitoring section.

YouTube ([@ai4eosc](https://www.youtube.com/@ai4eosc)⁵⁸)

This account showcases the explanatory animation movie, the latest news about the project, and other audiovisual materials like interviews, demonstrations and recorded workshops.

Social network engagement strategy

The project has proposed a new plan for the social media involvement strategy - a monthly communication plan for X/Twitter for [@AI4EOSC](https://twitter.com/AI4EOSC)

First week: Theme of the month.

- To create a hashtag for the topic of the month and put it in all tweets.
- We publish relevant content on the topic: interesting facts, news articles and main results of the project (if any).

Second week: News and relevant events.

- We share relevant news related to EOSC and AI.
- We promote events that may be of interest to our followers.

Third week: Multimedia content #ai4eoscInWords

- We share images and videos related to the theme of the month or the project in general with the hashtag #ai4eoscInWords. Example: the research team sends us 1-minute videos (horizontal), explaining their role in AI4EOSC.

⁵⁶ <https://twitter.com/AI4EOSC>

⁵⁷ <https://mastodon.social/@ai4eosc>

⁵⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/@ai4eosc>

- We encourage followers to share their own Cloud or AI related media content.

Fourth week: Interaction with followers.

- We launch a question to the followers as a survey and then we answer the correct one with a post that contains the solution and its explanation.

4.5.4 Animation Video

A [two-minute explanatory video](#)⁵⁹ of the project has been created. It's been made available via the project's web page and the official YouTube channel. It received over a hundred visits in its first month online

Agata Communications was in charge of drafting the initial script, which was later discussed and enriched by several partners thanks to their participation and input. A number of iterations were carried out before finding a visual message agreed upon by all and having it published in May 2023.

The goal of the video, created by [Xaime Beiro](#)⁶⁰, is to explain in a simple, accessible and engaging way the AI4EOSC project's goals. Several use cases are featured in the video, such as automated thermography, agrometeorology or integrated plant protection. Besides, it encourages scientists to keep expanding the EOSC by using the AI4EOSC platform.

4.5.5 Events

As part of the dissemination management several events have been identified as opportunities for dissemination of the results. Those include scientific conferences, exhibitions, policy meetings and domain-specific events. The list is included in the dedicated confluence page and most significant events are listed on the website in the Events & News section. In the [Annex III](#) below we include a snapshot of the Events table, presenting opportunities for 2023 as well as attended events.

4.5.6 Others

Zenodo

A [Zenodo community](#)⁶¹ has been created already in the period reported for researchers under the AI4EOSC project who want to increase the visibility of their research outputs (journal articles, presentations, datasets, models and others),

⁵⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=85AGuBIZzv0>

⁶⁰ <https://www.xaimebeiro.com/>

⁶¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/ai4eosc/>

collaborate with other researchers, and ensure the quality of their research outputs. We will also start exploiting this Zenodo community to deposit all the AI modules developed within AI4EOSC and the related platforms, enabling the automatic depositing of the individual module releases.

4.6 MONITORING

Monitoring is a key section of a dissemination plan because it allows organizations to track the effectiveness of their dissemination efforts and make any necessary adjustments.

By monitoring the reach and impact of their dissemination efforts, organizations can ensure that they are effectively communicating their messages and achieving their goals.

Table 7. List of Key Performance Indicators for the dissemination plan.

Metric	Number of occurrences
Publications exploiting the AI4EOSC framework	5
Public services available based on AI4EOSC exchange applications	5
User workshops held	3
Collaborations with external industries, including SMEs	5
External use cases on-boarded	5
External user communities using AI4EOSC platform	5

A set of specific actions will be taken to achieve this objective, among which the following stand out:

- Setting goals and metrics:** The project establishes clear goals and metrics for the dissemination plan, such as the number of stakeholders reached, the number of interactions with stakeholders, and the number of adoption of the project's results. These goals and metrics could be used to track progress and determine the success of the dissemination plan. Table 1 sets out the objectives committed to by the consortium. In particular, a set of specific indicators for monitoring social media activity is described in Table 2.

- **Regular evaluation:** The consortium conducts regular evaluations of the dissemination plan to assess its effectiveness and identify areas for improvement. This could involve conducting surveys or interviews with stakeholders to gather feedback on the plan and its impact.
- **Engagement tracking:** The project tracks engagement with stakeholders through various channels, such as social media, email, and events. This could provide insight into the reach and impact of the dissemination plan and help to identify successful approaches and areas for improvement.
- **Adaptation:** The project adapts the dissemination plan based on feedback from stakeholders and the results of evaluations. This could involve updating the plan to reflect changing needs and priorities, as well as incorporating new approaches and techniques for reaching and engaging with stakeholders.

Table 8. List of specific Key Performance Indicators for social media channels.

Indicator	Number of occurrences
Followers across all social networks	750
Average of messages per month in Twitter	10
Average of messages per month in Mastodon	10
Videos published in Youtube by the end of the project	15

The registry of the metrics is available in [the internal confluence webpage](#)⁶².

As part of the monitoring process we have setup the registry of all the publications, presentations and other dissemination activities, it is being collected on [the internal confluence webpage](#)⁶³ and in [Annex IV](#) we include the snapshot of the activities since the beginning of the project.

Current figures for the metrics are shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Current value of Key Performance Indicators for the dissemination plan.

⁶²

<https://confluence.ifca.es/pages/viewpage.action?spaceKey=AI4&title=WP2+KPI+and+Metrics>

⁶³ <https://confluence.ifca.es/display/AI4/Dissemination+table>

		2023				2024		
Metric	Target	03	06	09	12	03	06	09
Publications exploiting the AI4EOSC framework	5	3	4	6	9	9	13	16
Public services available based on AI4EOSC exchange applications	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
User workshops held	3	0	1	1	2	3	5	5
Collaboration with external industries, including SME's	5	0	1	2	2	2	2	3
External use cases on-boarded	5	0	1	1	1	1	1	4
External user communities using AI4EOSC platform	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	2

The project has exceeded its KPI in terms of the number of the publications and the user workshops. Project almost reached the planned number of external use cases. In terms of the other KPIs related with exploitation they are expected to be significantly increased in the next phase of the project, as planned, also as a result of the Open Calls. We do not see at the moment risks related to achieving the expected targets.

Table 10. Current status of Key Performance Indicators for social media channels.

Indicator	Number of occurrences
Followers across all social networks	351/750 (September, 2024)
Average of messages per month in X/(Twitter) Last year	12.83/10 (September, 2024)
Average of messages per month in Mastodon	0/10 (inactive account)
Videos published in Youtube by the end of the project	7/15 (September, 2024)

In terms of the social media channels, the project has faced serious uncertainty related with Twitter and its acquisition by Elon Musk, changing its engagement model (making organic engagement more difficult at the time of writing this deliverable), as well as with the rebranding (now: X). As a countermeasure, we

created an account on Mastodon, that was supposed to be an alternative in case Twitter would not be any more viable option (back-up/mitigation plan). However in the end the situation with Twitter/X has been normalized, and Mastodon had a significant drop in the user base (it is estimated that it was 30% from 2.5 mln to 1.8 mln). As keeping the account on the media to be successful needs a lot of effort, we have decided to continue with the X/Twitter while keeping Mastodon as an inactive account.

Another important aspect is the risk related with the X/Twitter activity and number of the followers. As there is now a need to pay for verification of the status monthly, the general activity and engagement on the X/Twitter has been significantly decreased (as shown in different market statistics in 2023⁶⁴). With the new algorithms, it is more difficult to enlarge the community pool. Those are the reasons to note the potential risk of not reaching the number of 750 followers by the end of the project. Anyway, the project consortium will put more effort towards attracting more potential followers using different available communication channels, events, etc.

Besides, the AI4EOSC consortium would like to highlight the drift in the Twitter/X course as a tool for scientific communication and engagement. The X takeover and functionality change includes an overhaul of the verified accounts check marks system and the complete removal of news headlines from article links, leading to a perceived increase in misinformation messages. Moreover, the current social attitude and wider frame of mind resembles not a vibrant but a polarized opinion system, acting as a resonance chamber for some messages. Lastly, the difficulties in organic engagement makes it difficult to engage with a given community, and therefore different engagement channels outside social media will be explored.

4.7 NEXT STEPS

The project activities related to WP2 have already moved into to the most intensive period, into promotion campaign that will focus on the promotion of the release of the AI4EOSC platform, and through the process of the open calls campaigns in order to reach external use cases and communities for further exploitation of the results by both research and business users. Several workshops and training are planned in Autumn 2024 to be organized in addition to participation in the events both in the AI and EOSC exosystem. Project will continue active collaboration with the projects and EOSC Association and ecosystem as described in the 3.4. There are a lot of activities planned for the integration of the AI4EOSC platform with other project environments (the liaison

⁶⁴ <https://www.similarweb.com/amp/blog/insights/social-media-news/twitter-shrinking/>

has been initiated in the framework of WP2). Through a new webpage WP2 will actively promote the results of AI4EOSC - services, products and software stack. Several activities focused on the exploitation of the results will be intensified.

Key points and priorities till end of the project:

1. Collaboration and exploitation

- a. Broader collaborations outside of the EOSC ecosystem, as a means to make researchers aware of the EOSC added value. We have identified several opportunities to expand to the marine sciences community via iImagine, towards the life sciences community via AI4Life and towards industry via strategic collaborations and engagement with Flower Labs and NVIDIA.
- b. Strengthen the collaboration in the EOSC ecosystem, with the already identified projects in terms of technical federation and interoperability (namely RAISE and BlueCloud), exploring direct exploitation of FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT in terms of semantic interoperability, metadata and FAIRness of AI assets.

2. Dissemination and impact achievement

- a. Early work towards the launch of the next release of the AI4EOSC platform and the AI4OS software, underlying the integration with other platforms, services and repositories, as well as its interoperability features.
- b. Launch a second open call and campaign to onboard new use cases as a means to validate the solutions that are being delivered by AI4EOSC, engaging also with potential resource providers, or users with their own infrastructures.
- c. Focus the active participation and organization of the events at the following strategic events:
 - i. EGI Conference 2024: booth in exhibition area, oral presentations, live demonstrations and posters.
 - ii. EOSC Symposium 2024: Organization of the "FAIR data for AI and AI for FAIR data" plenary session.
 - iii. Active participation in the INFRAEOSC coordinators meeting organized by the European Commission in 2025.
 - iv. Participation in the EOSC Association Winter School/other general meetings, studying the co-location of an AI4EOSC project meeting in order to maximize participation and engagement.

3. Trainings and workshops:

- a. Planned 3 next online workshops regarding the technologies used in the project for developers and users of AI and AI4EOSC.
- b. Final face to face workshop for users, to be defined with potential collaborators (iMagine, AI4Life)

ANNEXES

I. DEFINITIONS

The Definitions Annex of the dissemination and exploitation plan for the AI4EOSC project includes the following definitions of key terms:

- **DIH:** It refers to the Digital Innovation Hub.
- **EOSC:** The European Open Science Cloud is a digital infrastructure that brings together existing scientific data and services from across Europe, making it easier for researchers to access, share, and reuse data in their work.
- **IPR:** It stands for "Intellectual Property Rights." In the context of the AI4EOSC project, this term refers to the legal rights that protect the project's results, such as patents, copyrights, and trademarks. These rights are important for ensuring that the project's results can be used and exploited in a way that is fair and beneficial to all project partners.
- **KER:** It refers to the Key Exploitable Results of a project.
- **SME:** It refers to Small and Medium-sized Entreprises that are defined in the [EU recommendation 2003/361](#)⁶⁵.
- **TRL:** It refers to the Technology Readiness Levels which is a measure of maturity for a technology or a project. A total of nine different levels are defined where the level 9 corresponds to a system proven in an operational environment.

⁶⁵ https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/smes/sme-definition_en

II. BRANDING KIT

The visual identity of the AI4EOSC project is built on the following materials:

Logo:

Logo variations:

For more logo variations see the [Communication Kit](#)⁶⁶.

⁶⁶ <https://ai4eosc.eu/communication-kit/>

Font:

The chosen font for the project is Roboto Regular. It guarantees good readability.

Uppercase

A B C D E F G H I J K
L M N O P Q R S T U
V W X Y Z

Lowercase

a b c d e f g h i j k l
m n o p q r s t u v w
x y z

Colors:

The two official brand colors for the EOSC logo are mild pink and lively emerald.

The color codes are as follows:

Pink

RGB 255/92/128
CMYK 0/76/27/0
#ff5b7f

Green

RGB 0/134/145
CMYK 90/0/33/25
#008792

For more color variations, please download the [Co-Branding Guidelines](#)⁶⁷.

⁶⁷ https://ai4eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/10/2023/02/20220614_EOSC_Co-Branding-Guidelines_1_EOSC-A.pdf

III. EVENTS TABLE

Event Name	Date	Location	Opportunity description	Partner(s) to Attend	URL	Status
ISGC 25	March 25	Taiwan	International Symposium on Grids & Clouds	IISAS	https://indico4.twgrid.org/event/51/	planned
EOSC Symposium	October 24	Berlin	EOSC ecosystem major event	PSNC, CSIC	https://eosc.eu/symposium2024/	planned
IBERGrid 24	October 24	Porto	Regional event related with EOSC	CSIC, UPV, IISAS	https://www.ibergrid.eu/	planned
EASiNet CrossTalk event	October 24	Brussels	International workshop/seminar	CSIC		planned
Agroshow 24	September 24	Bednary Poland	Largest Agriculture fairs with over 120 000 attendees	PSNC, WODR	https://www.agroshow.pl/agroshow/en	planned
EGI2024	September 24	Lecce	Submitted presentations + booth+posters. The annual EGI conference is widely recognised as the venue that brings together like-minded professionals from the world of science and scientific computing. This year we have a specific topic in AI.	CSIC, PSNC, IISAS, WODR, UPV	https://www.egi.eu/event/egi2024/	planned

Event Name	Date	Location	Opportunity description	Partner(s) to Attend	URL	Status
KES'2024	Sep 2024	Seville	Presentation and publication of a paper about federated learning (FL) and Differential Privacy. The output (paper) will be in Procedia Computer Science, Elsevier.	IISAS	http://kes2024.kesinternational.org/	attended
The 2nd IEEE International Conference on Federated Learning Technologies and Applications	May 24	Valencia	Event regarding Federated Learning that will be held at Universitat Politècnica de València	UPV	https://flta-conference.org/	attended
12th ACM Workshop on Information Hiding and Multimedia Security	June 24	Baiona, Spain	Special session on Security and Privacy Challenges towards Trustworthy Federated Learning	CSIC	https://www.ihmmsec.org/cms/home/home173.html?acceptCookie=1&idart=205&idcat=69&changelang=2	attended
Helmholtz AI Conference 2024: AI for Science	June 24	Düsseldorf, Germany	Present any of AI4EOSC-related activities (FL, project, MLOps)	KIT	https://haicon24.de/	attended

Event Name	Date	Location	Opportunity description	Partner(s) to Attend	URL	Status
AI4Life workshop: Zero-code tools & BMZ Community partners	June 24	Madrid, Spain	Present the AI4EOOSC project and seek new synergies and collaboration opportunities with other European AI-related projects, such as AI4Life.	CSIC	https://ai4life.eurobioimaging.eu/event/workshop-hackathon-uploathon-madrid/	attended
Flower AI Summit 2024	March 24	London	The world's largest Federated Learning conference. Introducing the AI4EOOSC project, the EOOSC and how to train a FL model within the AI4EOOSC platform. Talk entitled: Federated AI in the European Open Science Cloud	CSIC	https://flower.ai/conf/flower-ai-summit-2024/	attended
IEEE 23rd International Symposium on Computational Intelligence and Informatics (CINTI 2023) Conference	20-22.11.2023	Budapest, Hungary	Presentation and publication of a paper: A State-of-the-Art Survey on Local Training Methods in Federated Learning	IISAS	https://conf.uni-obuda.hu/cinti2023/	attended
AI4EOOSC Platform: User's workshop	15-16.11.2023	Bratislava, Slovakia	User workshop for local organization purposes	CSIC, IISAS, KIT, Microstep-MIS, UPV, PSNC, WODR	https://indico.scc.kit.edu/event/3845/	attended

Event Name	Date	Location	Opportunity description	Partner(s) to Attend	URL	Status
ECMWF Code For Earth	20-21.09.2023	Bologna, Italy	Code for Earth is an innovation programme run by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). Its aim is to drive innovation and open source developments in the Earth sciences community - supporting developments in weather and climate, Copernicus and Destination Earth (DestinE). Predictia presented the DeepR project, which used AI4EOSC resources. The aim of the project is to create a Machine learning (ML) model that can generate high-resolution regional reanalysis data (similar to the one produced by CERRA) by downscaling global reanalysis data from ERA5. This was accomplished by using state-of-the-art Deep Learning (DL) techniques like U-Net, conditional GAN, and diffusion models (among others). Additionally, an ingestion module will be implemented to assess the possible benefit of using CERRA pseudo-observations as extra predictors. Once the model is designed and trained, a detailed validation framework takes the place.	Predictia	https://codeforearth.ecmwf.int/	attended

Event Name	Date	Location	Opportunity description	Partner(s) to Attend	URL	Status
IEEE 21st International Symposium on Intelligent Systems and Informatics (SISY) 2023 Conference	21-22.09.2023	Pula, Croatia	Presentation and publication of a paper: Classification of Tree Species by Federated Learning	IISAS	https://conf.uni-obuda.hu/sisy2023/index.html	attended
EOSC Symposium 2023	20-22.09.2023	Madrid, Spain	The main EOSC annual event. Stakeholders from ministries, policy makers, research performing organisations, service providers, research infrastructures and research communities across Europe and beyond are expected to attend the Symposium to reflect on the EOSC key achievements and strategic challenges and to identify priorities and concrete actions at European, national, and institutional level to speed up the EOSC implementation.	PSNC	https://symposium23.eosc-future.eu/	attended
SQAMIA 2023	9.2023	Bratislava, Slovakia	The 10th Workshop on Software Quality Analysis, Monitoring, Improvement, and Applications. Presentation and publication of a paper (Data Partitioning Effects in Federated Learning, in print).	IISAS	http://sqamia.org/	attended

Event Name	Date	Location	Opportunity description	Partner(s) to Attend	URL	Status
Ibergrid 2023	25-29.09.2023	Benasque, Spain	IBERGRID 2023 will focus on topics related with the development, integration, quality and adoption of services, applications and digital twins to support cutting-edge research.	UPV, KIT	https://www.ibergrid.eu/2023-ibergrid-benasque/	attended
IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience	31.07-2.08.2023	Venice, Italy	Presentation and publication of a paper⁶⁸ . Creation of synergies with colleagues working on other projects especially in relation to FL, HE, etc. Attendance to IEEE CSR Workshop on Privacy-Preserving Data Processing and Analysis (2P-DPA).	CSIC	https://www.ieee-csr.org/	attended
AIHUB CSIC	3-7.07.2023	Barcelona, Spain	Synergies on artificial intelligence tools and methods. Poster presentation on the application of federated learning (highly related to the scope of the project) to medical imaging environments.	CSIC	https://aihub.csic.es/programa-retos-de-la-ia-2023/	attended
Teledetección como herramienta global	10-14.07.2023	Santander, Spain	Reach out additional use cases and the larger remote sensing community in Spain	CSIC	https://www.uimp.es/agenda-link.html?id_actividad=65IN&anyaca=2023-24	attended

⁶⁸ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10224917>

Event Name	Date	Location	Opportunity description	Partner(s) to Attend	URL	Status
EGI Conference 2023	19-23.06.2023	Poznan, Poland	The annual EGI conference is widely recognised as the venue that brings together like-minded professionals from the world of science and scientific computing.	PSNC, UPV, KIT, CSIC, IISAS	https://eosc.eu/events/egi-conference-2023	attended
Krajowe Dni Pola 2023	3-5.06.2023	Sielinko (near Opalenica), Poland	Integrated plant protection use case roll-up/presentation presentation about the use case. Public, farmers, agriculture machinery producers, domain experts, area of innovation. Booth of the project	WODR, PSNC	https://www.dnipola2023.pl/	attended
ISC High Performance 2023	22 - 24.05.2023	Hamburg, DE	ISC High Performance 2023 is an international conference and exhibition that fosters the growth of a global HPC community of technology providers and users. ISC 2023 will be held from May 21 – 25 in Hamburg, Germany, and expects over 3,000 international attendees.	KIT	https://www.isc-hpc.com/submissions-project-posters-2023.html	attended

Event Name	Date	Location	Opportunity description	Partner(s) to Attend	URL	Status
Regionalne Targi Rolnicze Gołaszyn	20-21.05.2023	Gołaszyn, Poland	Integrated plant protection use case roll-up/presentation presentation about the use case. Public, farmers, agriculture machinery producers, domain experts	WODR	https://www.wodr.poznan.pl/wydarzenia/wydarzenia-wodr	attended
Wiosenne Targi Rolno-Ogrodnicze AGROMARSZ	02.04.2023	Marszew, Poland	Integrated plant protection use case presentation about the use case roll-up/presentation Public, farmers, agriculture machinery producers, domain experts	WODR	https://www.wodr.poznan.pl/wydarzenia/wydarzenia-wodr	attended
The 14th International Conference on Ambient Systems, Networks and Technologies, ANT 2023	15 - 17.03.2023	Leuven, Belgium	Presentation and publication of a paper about federated learning (FL), Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC) about medical imaging inference with HE. The output (published paper) is in Procedia Computer Science, Elsevier, vol. 220, pp. 24-31.	IISAS	http://cs-conferences.acadiau.ca/ant-23/#	attended

IV. DISSEMINATION TABLE

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
Computer Science course	general	WP2, All	general talk about the project	Lessons	September 2022 - February 2023	Bratislava	IISAS (with FIIT STU)	Intelligent Data Analysis /Introduction to Data Science course	https://github.com/FIIT-IAU/IAU-course
					September 2023 - February 2024				
Presentation	general	WP2, All	general presentation about the project	Meeting of the cluster of projects with EOSC Association in Brussels	30-Sep-22	Brussels	PSNC	-	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1uBwY7yAVWpEbEkSVzeslDdTGT6yo8xDfRLCBumRCMc4/edit#slide=id.p1
Presentation	general	WP2, All	general presentation about the project	IberGrid	Oct-22	Faro	PSNC	https://indico.lip.pt/event/1249/timetable/#20221012	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1B7UZvvGnHdXMJpGEYMxWwuUksipCulDu-zwYz_cTm8l/edit?usp=sharing

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
Presentation	general	All	general presentation about the project	EGI Conference	21-Sep-22	Prague	KIT	https://indico.egi.eu/event/5882/	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1o5UXs-aQRAKPfJjHiLyR5bU6tqtTQad-AXQBN3zyRs/edit?usp=sharing
Presentation	Integrated plant protection use case	WP2, WP6	presentation about the use case	Agroshow Bednary	Sep-22	Bednary/Poznan	PSNC, WODR	https://www.agroshow.pl/agroshow/en/	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1RMpVpyJWS2e9KW3pK7koBSF8R9WA9NuJ?usp=sharing
Presentation	general	All	general presentation about the project	EOSC Symposium	15-Nov-22	Prague	IFCA	https://events.eoscfuture.eu/symposium2022/2606111	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/15ei7f1t5jgDPaIgv3S1Ns7SbduJe85kFMPs61jzloHQ/edit?usp=sharing

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
Presentation	general	All	general presentation about the project	High-Performance Computing (HPC) and Data-Intensive Computing (DIC) User Meeting	13-Jan-23	Karlsruhe, Germany (virtual)	KIT	https://www.scc.kit.edu/en/cooperations/13191.php	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1F2I5DaQOs4ZBcVR9I4-AQIQD1v4_3MGZONKqBWgWNqU/edit?usp=share_link Meeting slides: https://bwsyncandshare.kit.edu/s/sDWRcamggGo9Z59?dir=undefined&path=%2F2023-01-13
Invited Talk	general	WP2, All	general talk about the project	Invited Talk at INRIA	22-Sep-22	Rennes	IISAS (with FIIT STU)	SUPSEC: AI for supervision	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1qdqL8A4jXiLDPVnAp2OAGG0NCUYGgODmRc4HzxeFeA/presentation#slide=id.p
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	Jan-23		IISAS		https://www.ui.sav.sk/w/en/horizon-europe/#an_1_002 https://www.ui.sav.sk/w/horizont-europa/#an_1_002 (Slovak)

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	Jan-23		KIT (SCC)		https://www.scc.kit.edu/en/research/16595.php
									https://www.scc.kit.edu/forschung/16595.php (German)
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	Jan-23		Predictia		https://predictia.es/en/projects/ai4eosc
									https://predictia.es/es/projects/ai4eosc (Spanish)
									News:
									https://predictia.es/en/news/ai4eosc
								https://predictia.es/es/news/ai4eosc (Spanish)	
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	Jan-23		UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA		https://www.grycap.upv.es/index.php/ai4eosc/
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the	AI4EOSC project	Jan-23		MicroStep-MIS		https://www.microstep-mis.com/web/about-us?tab=Projects

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
			project						<p><u>News:</u> https://www.microstep-mis.com/web/news/other/ai_for_the_european_open_science_cloud</p>
post on social media	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	Jan-23		MicroStep-MIS		<p><u>LinkedIn:</u> https://www.linkedin.com/company/microstep-mis</p> <p><u>Twitter:</u> https://twitter.com/MstepMIS/status/1610925669436858373?s=20&t=OL_U63wu0xfXB4HREZPAMw</p> <p><u>Facebook:</u> https://www.facebook.com/MicroStepMIS</p> <p><u>Instagram:</u> https://www.instagram.com/p/CnByZ7CLIOJ/</p>
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	Jan-23		PSNC		<p>https://www.psnk.pl/projects/ai4eosc/</p> <p>https://www.pcss.pl/projekty/ai4eosc/ (Polish)</p>

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	Jan-23		CSIC		CSIC: https://www.csic.es/es/actualidad-del-csic/el-csic-lidera-un-proyecto-europeo-para-impulsar-el-uso-de-la-inteligencia
									University of Cantabria: https://web.unican.es/noticias/Paginas/2022/octubre_2022/proyecto-ia-IFCA.aspx
									IFCA: https://ifca.unican.es/es-es/news/Paginas/IFCA-lidera-proyecto-europeo-impulsar-inteligencia-artificial-mas-avanzada.aspx
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	Jan-23		KIT (IIP)		https://www.iip.kit.edu/english/460_6075.php
									https://www.iip.kit.edu/460_6075.php (German)

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	Jan-23		WODR		https://www.wodr.poznan.pl/alias-projekty/ai4eosc
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	Apr-23		INFN		https://www.ba.infn.it/it/fondi_esterni/#AI4EOSC (Italian)
Demonstration	general	WP4/ WP5	Showcase IM	Infrastructure Manager (IM): TOSCA deployment and orchestration in the Cloud Continuum	Jun-23	Poznan, Poland	UPV	https://www.egi.eu/event/egi2023	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=U0wvPjPzjHs
Demonstration	general	WP4/ WP5	Showcase OSCAR	Serverless Computing with OSCAR in EGI: Integration with Jupyter NoteBooks and dCache	Jun-23	Poznan, Poland	UPV	https://www.egi.eu/event/egi2023	Integration with dCache: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mpy8veWS-ss Integration with EGI Notebooks: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OgrVVAJJtc8

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
Training	general	WP6	How to build AI application /service based on existing AI modules	Training: Bringing your AI models to EOSC. Part 1. Build AI application /service based on existing AI modules using the AI4EOSC platform	Jun-23	Poznan, Poland	CSIC	https://www.egi.eu/event/egi2023	
Training	general	WP6	Building DEEPaaS API for Existing Model	Training: Bringing your AI models to EOSC. Part 2. Develop a new AI application / service with the AI4EOSC platform	Jun-23	Poznan, Poland	KIT	https://www.egi.eu/event/egi2023	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/14QVu3ZTijlmS8gyBeljXZUPhafVY2Han/ https://git.scc.kit.edu/m-team/ai/ai4eosc-egi23-tutorial/-/blob/main/ai4eosc-tutorial.ipynb

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
Training	general	WP4/ WP5	Use OSCAR for AI model inference	Training: Bringing your AI models to EOSC. Part 3. Deploy your AI-based service for inference using the AI4EOSC platform	Jun-23	Poznan, Poland	UPV	https://www.egi.eu/event/egi2023	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1_CmhMmhgRmwYrMJJaTWgWneihAn2c1DDf1w6sq9hkzrU/edit?usp=sharing
Lighttalk	general	WP6	Review existing MLOps solutions: to efficiently put ML models into production and monitoring drift detection	Landscaping MLOps Solutions: AI4EOSC Case Study	Jun-23	Poznan, Poland	KIT and CSIC	https://www.egi.eu/event/egi2023	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1Fc860iGluBWv9mpeOr_D5Zo7iAZkoxuA/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=115105737741477619886&rtpof=true&sd=true
Talk	general	WP5		Towards DataLab as a service	Jun-23	Poznan, Poland	CSIC	https://www.egi.eu/event/egi2023	

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
Talk	general	All	Showcase AI4EOSC	Empowering EOSC scientists with AI services and tools	Jun-23	Poznan, Poland	CSIC	https://www.egi.eu/event/egi2023	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1PIJKLhGbtshNLXu25V3B14LJWv7gyhGTA-at3PUqpxM/edit#slide=id.p1
Talk	general	WP4/ WP5	Showcase DEEPaaS	DEEPaaS API: The Community API for AI in the EOSC	Jun-23	Poznan, Poland	CSIC	https://www.egi.eu/event/egi2023	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1LcvsszSLRPJ_RLCN87-K-aEY-470kp5meyVcV4el9gU/edit#slide=id.p1
Talk	general	WP4/ WP5	Showcase platform	Distributed computing platform on EGI Federated Cloud	Jun-23	Poznan, Poland	CSIC	https://www.egi.eu/event/egi2023	
Poster presentation	general	WP6, all	General presentation about project the	Helmholtz Program EDF, meeting of the international Strategic Advisory Board	Jul-2023	Karlsruhe, Germany	KIT		

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
Poster presentation	general	WP4	Federated learning application	Application of federated learning to medical imaging scenarios	Jul-23	Barcelona, Spain	CSIC	https://aihub.csic.es/escuela-de-verano-aihub/	2023/07 - Application of federated learning to medical imaging scenarios
Conference talk: paper presentation	general	WP4	Machine learning application and data privacy	Comparison of machine learning models applied on anonymized data with different techniques	Aug-23	Venice, Italy	CSIC	https://www.ieee-csr.org/	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10224917
Demonstration	general	WP5	Showcase AI4Compose	AI4Compose: low-code composition of AI inference pipelines	Sep-23	Benasque (Spain)	UPV	https://www.ibergrid.eu/	https://indico.lip.pt/event/1543/contributions/5118/
Demonstration	general	WP4	Showcase IM	Infrastructure Manager: A decade of innovation in virtualised infrastructure provisioning	Sep-23	Benasque (Spain)	UPV	https://www.ibergrid.eu/	https://indico.lip.pt/event/1543/contributions/5116/

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
Demonstration	general	WP7	Showcase of Infrastructure service	Service Migration and High Availability Using Dynamic DNS Service	Sep-23	Benasque (Spain)	IISAS	https://www.ibergrid.eu/	https://indico.lip.pt/event/1543/contributions/5209/
Demonstration	general	WP7	Showcase of Infrastructure service	Supporting Native Cloud Tools in the EGI Federated Cloud via the FedCloud Client	Sep-23	Benasque (Spain)	IISAS	https://www.ibergrid.eu/	https://indico.lip.pt/event/1543/contributions/5214/
Demonstration	general	WP7	Showcase of Infrastructure service	Lockers: An Innovative and Secure Solution for Managing Secrets in the EGI Cloud Infrastructure	Sep-23	Benasque (Spain)	IISAS	https://www.ibergrid.eu/	https://indico.lip.pt/event/1543/contributions/5212/
Demonstration	general	WP4/ WP5	Showcase OSCAR	Serverless Scientific Computing with OSCAR	Sep-23	Benasque (Spain)	UPV	https://www.ibergrid.eu/	https://indico.lip.pt/event/1543/contributions/5121/

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
Keynote	general	All	Computing and AI in EOSC	Computing and AI in EOSC - Opportunities & Future outlook	Oct-23	Virtual	CSIC	https://docs.google.com/document/d/e/2PACX-1vSMFfLIifogv98dRiCs2FpYSbmTQNoqspUFuE27YcbuKWx0IIgwOj3J4quAKPOjzZA/pub	
Talk	use case	WP6	General presentation	Webinar talk in "ANERIS Workshops on AI Basics for Image Processing" : UAV-based Thermography: Using AI with Multispectral Data	Dec-23	Virtual	KIT	https://aneris.eu/news/aneris-workshops-ai-basics-image-processing	
Post on social media	general	WP6	Short video introducing AI4EOSC use cases	AI4EOSC project	Oct-23	online	CSIC		
Post on social media	general	WP6	Short video introducing AI4EOSC use cases	AI4EOSC project	Oct-23	online	MicroStep-MIS		

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
Post on social media	general	WP6	Short video introducing AI4EOSC use cases	AI4EOSC project	Nov-23	online	KIT		
Post on social media	general	WP6	Short video introducing AI4EOSC use cases	AI4EOSC project	Dec-23	online	PSNC		
Talk	general, FL	WP1, WP4	Talkat Flower Monthly (January)	FL with flower in the EOSC	Jan-24	online	CSIC	https://flower.dev/conf/flower-monthly/	
News about the open call, AI4EOSC 1 release and webinars	general	ALL	News on the webpage	AI4EOSC project	March-24	online	CISC	https://ifca.unican.es/es-es/news/Paginas/El-IFCA-participa-AI4EOSC-1-nueva-herramienta-desarrollar-modelos-IA-en-nube-ciencia-abierta.aspx	

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
News about AI4EOSC webinars	general	ALL	News on the webpage	AI4EOSC project	March-24	online	KIT	https://www.scc.kit.edu/ueberuns/17468.php	
Presentation at AI in AEC (AI in Architecture, Engineering and Construction) 2024 conference	UC3	WP6	UC3 AI model	AI in multispectral image analysis: Implementing a deep learning model for the segmentation of common thermal urban features to assist in the automation of infrastructure-related maintenance	March-24	Helsinki, Finland	KIT	https://www.ril.fi/en/events/ai-in-aec-2024/	
News about AI4EOSC First release and the Open Call	general	ALL	News on the webpage	AI4EOSC project	April-24	online	KIT	https://www.scc.kit.edu/ueberuns/17496.php	

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
Post on social media about the open call, AI4EOSC 1 release and webinars	general	ALL	Info about the project achievements and activities	AI4EOSC project	April-24	online	MicroStep-MIS	https://www.facebook.com/MicroStepMIS https://www.linkedin.com/company/5296466/admin/feed/posts/ https://twitter.com/MstepMIS https://www.linkedin.com/company/5296466/admin/feed/posts/ https://twitter.com/MstepMIS	

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
Webinar	project wide	WP4	AI Inference with OSCAR	Deploy you AI-based service for inference using OSCAR	an-24	online	UPV		https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1YjUY29d4QGF_rhLoWCKws0dlpzkDQKln2P0G6poAMaQ/edit
RICH Europe's first Symposium of Research Infrastructures	project wide	ALL	Invited talk for AI4EOSC	Invited talk for AI4EOSC	Jun-24	In person	CISC	https://rich-europe.eu/events/1st-symposium-of-research-infrastructures/	
ESFRI-EOSC Policy Workshop on "FAIR Data Productivity and Advanced Digitalization"	project wide	ALL	Invited talk for AI4EOSC	Invited talk for AI4EOSC	Jan-24	in person	CSIC	https://www.esfri.eu/esfri-events/policy-workshop-fair-data	
Presentantion	general	WP5	iMagine Competence Centre Workshop	iMagine AI Platform updates and feedback collection	March-24	in person	CSIC	https://indico.egi.eu/event/6371/	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1sO8wwsKUOb40eKqwDWOLhExdvOYu-G8vHvawtdXMZ-U/edit#slide=id.g2bbf67c4d39_8_0

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
News	general	all	News in the webpage	AI4EOSC project	April-2024	online	IIAS	https://www.sav.sk/?lang=sk&doc=services-news&source_no=20&news_no=11890	
News	general	all	News in the webpage	AI4EOSC project	April-2024	online	IIAS	https://eraportal.sk/aktualita/projekt-ai4eosc-spusta-subornastrojov-pre-umelu-inteligenciu-a-otvorenu-vyzvu-na-nove-pripady-pouzitia	

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
Press release	general	all	Press	AI4EOSC Project	April 2024	online	IIAS	https://bleskovky.zoznam.sk/cl/1005001/2747643/Sav-je-partnerom-europskeho-projektu-zameraneho-na-vyuzitie-umelej-inteligencie https://www.teraz.sk/slovensko/sav-je-partnerom-projektu-eu-o-vyuzit/791529-clanok.htm https://zive.aktuality.sk/clanok/ReJahtt/novy-impulz-pre-umelu-inteligenciu-na-slovensku-sav-je-partnerom-europskeho-projektu-zameraneho-na-ai/	https://zive.aktuality.sk/clanok/ReJahtt/novy-impulz-pre-umelu-inteligenciu-na-slovensku-sav-je-partnerom-europskeho-projektu-zameraneho-na-ai/

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
Poster presentation	general	all	General presentation about the project	AI4EOSC: customizable AI platform in the EOSC context	June 2024	Düsseldorf, Germany	KIT	https://haicon24.de/	
Poster presentation	general, FL	WP4, 6	Federated learning application	Federated Learning for Urban Energy Efficiency: Detecting Thermal Anomalies with UAV-based Imaging and AI	June 2024	Düsseldorf, Germany	KIT	https://haicon24.de/	
Poster presentation	FL	WP4, 6	Federated learning application	Investigating Data Distribution Variability Across Devices in Federated Learning: Comparative Analysis of Algorithm Performance	June 2024	Düsseldorf, Germany	KIT	https://haicon24.de/	
Poster presentation	general, MLOps	WP5, 6	MLOps	AI/ML drift detection monitoring system	June 2024	Düsseldorf, Germany	KIT	https://haicon24.de/	

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
Poster presentation	Use case	WP6	Experiments with one of the UC3 AI models	How Does Feature Engineering Impact UAV-based Multispectral Semantic Segmentation? An RGB and Thermal Image Ablation Study	June 2024	Düsseldorf, Germany	KIT	https://haicon24.de/	
Presentation during Fairs	General, use case	WP2, 6	UC2 use case related to the agriculture related products and research	AI4EOSC: general presentation on the booth during the Fields Days 2024	June 2024	Sielinko, Poznań	PSNC, WODR	https://www.wodr.poznan.pl/wydarzenia/krajowe-dni-pola-2023	
Presentation	General	WP3	EC organised concertation meeting of EOSC cluster projects	AI4EOSC: Contributing to uptake of AI in research: advanced AI for scientists - the AI4EOSC platform	June 2024	Brussels	PSNC	https://eosc.eu/events/2024-coordination-meeting-of-eosc-related-projects-funded-under-horizon-europe/	

V. LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

Title	Type of publication	Journal/Conference	Relevance to project	Date	Partner involved	Other comments
An improved sea lion optimization for workload elasticity prediction with neural networks	Peer-reviewed journal	International Journal of Computational Intelligence Systems	ML/DL	October 2022	IISAS	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s44196-022-00156-8
Study of the performance and scalability of federated learning for medical imaging with intermittent clients	Peer-reviewed journal	Neurocomputing	FL	November 2022	CSIC	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0925231222013844
A Python library to check the level of anonymity of a dataset	Peer-reviewed journal	Scientific data	Data privacy	December 2022	CSIC	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-022-01894-2

Title	Type of publication	Journal/Conference	Relevance to project	Date	Partner involved	Other comments
Secure Multi-Party Computation for Magnetic Resonance Imaging Classification	Peer-reviewed journal	Procedia Computer Science	SMPC	April 2023	IISAS	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050923005410?via%3Dihub
Infrastructure Manager: A TOSCA-based Orchestrator for the Computing Continuum	Peer-reviewed journal	Journal of Grid Computing	IM	August 2023	UPV	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10723-023-09686-7
Comparison of machine learning models applied on anonymized data with different techniques	Peer-reviewed conference	2023 IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience (CSR)	Data privacy	August 2023	CSIC	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10224917

Title	Type of publication	Journal/Conference	Relevance to project	Date	Partner involved	Other comments
Deep learning based soft-sensor for continuous chlorophyll estimation on decentralized data	Peer-reviewed journal	Water research	DL	October 2023	CSIC	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2023.120726
Data Partitioning Effects in Federated Learning	Peer-reviewed conference	CEUR Workshop Proceedings	Federated Learning	December 2023	IIAS	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10378239
Rescheduling Serverless Workloads Across the Cloud-to-Edge Continuum	Peer-reviewed journal	Future Generation Computer Systems	serverless Workloads	December 2023	UPV	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167739X23004764?via%3Dihub

Title	Type of publication	Journal/Conference	Relevance to project	Date	Partner involved	Other comments
Making Federated Learning Accessible to Scientists: The AI4EOSC Approach	Peer-reviewed conference	Information Hiding and Multimedia Security 2024 (IH&MMSEC), Baiona, Spain	Federated Learning	June 2024	CSIC, IISAS	https://doi.org/10.1145/3658664.3659642
Network security AIOps for online stream data monitoring	Peer-reviewed journal	Neural Computing and Applications	AIOps, DL, NN, Network security, deployment	April 2024	IISAS, CSIC	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00521-024-09863-z
Frouros: An open-source Python library for drift detection in machine learning systems	Peer-reviewed journal	SoftwareX	Drift detection, MLOps	May 2024	CSIC	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352711024001043?via%3Dihub

Title	Type of publication	Journal/Conference	Relevance to project	Date	Partner involved	Other comments
Efficient and scalable covariate drift detection in machine learning systems with serverless computing	Peer-reviewed journal	Future Generation Computer Systems	Drift detection, Serverless computing	July 2024	CSIC, UPV	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167739X24003716
Personalized Federated Learning for improving radar based precipitation nowcasting on heterogeneous areas	Peer-reviewed journal	Earth Sciences Informatics	FL, UC1	August 2024	CSIC, MicroStep, KIT	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12145-024-01438-9
Optimal Differential Privacy for Deep Learning Model Training	Peer-reviewed journal	Procedia Computer Science	differential privacy, DL	September 2024	IISAS	Accepted

Title	Type of publication	Journal/Conference	Relevance to project	Date	Partner involved	Other comments
Detecting District Heating Leaks in Thermal Imagery: Comparison of Anomaly Detection Methods	Peer-reviewed journal	Automation in Construction	UC3	September 2024	KIT	Accepted`
Big Data Deduplication in Data Lake	Peer-reviewed journal	Acta Polytechnica Hungarica	cloud computing, big data	September 2024	IISAS	Accepted

